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When we look at our ancient history, we know that certain specialized ways have appeared since the Bronze Age of human society, and in some places much earlier. Their emergence was caused by economic, ethnic, political and cultural needs arising from tribes, peoples and interstate relations. In history, we know that during the reign of Iran's Akhmenids in the VI-IV centuries BC, a "royal road" was formed along its territory. But until then, the need for Badakhshan lapis lazuli in the Middle and Middle East led to the creation of the "Lazurite Road". One such ancient road was the "Great Silk Road", which connected the West and the East for several thousand years. Although the trade goods that flowed from the East (from China) to the West (Byzantium) through this road were mainly Chinese silk, this road was discovered only in the 70s of the

"THE GREAT SILK ROAD"

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the "Great Silk" road, which left an important mark in the history of the ancient world in terms of trade, played an important role in the harmony of the cultures of the East and the West, served to connect the East and the West, and played an important role. and the origin of the "Great Silk" road in later times, its development in the Middle Ages, including its important tasks during the period of the Timurid state, its development during the Russian colonial period, after the collapse of the Soviet Union, it was carried out within the framework of the "Great Silk" road the significance of the work done for the present time is discussed and analyzed.

XIX century by the German scientist K. Richthofen called "Silk Road". It was introduced. Until then, "Silk Road" was called "West Meridional Road". The first written information about the "Great Silk Road" dates back to 138 BC: Zhang Xiang, an ambassador and traveler sent to Central Asia by the Chinese emperor Wu Di, discovered the "Great Silk Road". researches and gives its classification accordingly. During this period, the Huns were plundering the northern regions of China, and Emperor Zhang sent Xiang to find allies and partners in the fight against the nomadic Hun tribes. The ambassador was captured by the Huns and was imprisoned for ten years. He escapes from captivity and goes to Issyk-kol through the Central Tian'shan passes. It comes along the Norin River to the Ferghana Valley. Here he discovers the cities of the valley for

himself. He learns that these cities belong to the kingdom of Ferghana. Naturally, the ambassador wants to get the help of the ruler of Ferghana in China's fight against the Huns. But the ruler of Ferghana only expresses his desire to establish trade relations. Zhang Xiang continues his journey to the south. Passing through the Aloy Valley, it again falls into the hands of the Huns. He returns to his homeland after a year. The ambassador tells the Chinese emperor about his trip. He took one of Ferghana's horses and alfalfa seeds to China. The Chinese called this horse heavenly. Emperor Wu Di planted clover near his palace. Later, it will be planted throughout the north of China. The Chinese also plant pomegranates, grapes, cucumbers and walnuts. Thus, along the road traveled by Zhang Xian, there was a ladder road called the Great Silk Road, connecting China with Central and Western Asia in the II-I centuries BC. The "Silk Road" starts from Xi'an, the ancient center of China, and reaches Dunhuang via Lanzhou. In Dunhuang, it splits into two. The southwestern branch of the "Silk Road" reached Khotan through the Takla-Makon desert, from there to Yorkent, through the gorges of the Pamir Mountains to Vakhan, from there to Zariaspa (Balkh), the capital of Bactria. Its western branch went to Marv, its southern branch to India, and its northern branch went to Darband, Nautak, Samarkand through Termiz. The northwestern branch of the "Silk Road" went from Dulhuan to Bami Kuchi, Turfan to the Tarim Oasis - Kashgar. From there through Tashkurgan, Ozgan, Osh, Guva, Akhsikent, Ponga, from there through the Asht steppe to Khojand, Zomin, Jizzakh, and then to Samarkand by the Nautaka road. The road passed from Samarkand to the

west - to Dobusia, through the Malik desert to Bukhara and Romitan, from there through Varakhsha to Paykent and Farob to the city of Amul. Amulda joined the road from Marv to Urganch along Amu. In ancient times, the city of Marv was the largest city on the Silk Road, due to its ancient traditions and geographic convenience, where trade caravan routes connected in all directions. Therefore, apart from the temples of local religion - Zoroastrianism, Marv had the foundations of Indian Buddhism and Byzantine Christianity. The ancient Silk Road was a great caravan and trade route from Marv to the West based on the "Lazuriot Road" and "King's Road" from this region to China, India and the Middle East. and connected with the Mediterranean countries. According to historical written sources and archeological materials, the silk road that went from Marv to the west went to the Iranian cities of Hekotolepil, Apalia and Ecbatana (Hamadon), and after them to the Mesopotamian cities of Ctesaphon and Baghdad. From there, he went north along the right bank of the Tigris River, passed through Angiohia (Antocia) to Damascus, and then to Egypt through the cities of Tire and Jerusalem. The northern road from Marv went through Amul to Urganch, from there along the North Caspian to the North Caucasus, then from the north of the Black Sea to Constantinople, passed through the Bosphorus and Dardanelles to the Mediterranean Sea, and connected the cities of Byzantium. Chinese emperors had trade and diplomatic relations with the countries located west of the Silk Road. They sent their ambassadors with great gifts to the countries of Central Asia, Iran, Mesopotamia and Asia Minor. For example, the Chinese traveler Gap In reached the

Persian Gulf in 97 AD. May Tisian from Macedonia reached Lanzhou in 100. But Central Asians and Iranians were never interested in the formation of direct trade relations between China and Byzantium or between China and Middle Eastern countries. Because "underneath" this movement was a very big economic policy. Especially, since the 3rd century, the struggle for the Silk Road has taken the form of a life-and-death struggle between Iran and Central Asia. In this regard, Iran and Parthia fought fiercely. The trade caravan routes passing from China to the west through Central Asia were always under the control of the Sugdians. In order to maintain their dominance on this route, the Sughd merchants established their caravanserais and villages in Eastern Turkestan, Ettisuv, in the regions from Altai to the banks of the Yenisei, in Shanxi region of Northern China, and in a number of cities such as Dunhuang. In the 3rd-7th centuries, the control of the "Silk Road" through Central Asia and the Middle East was in the hands of the Sugdians, but by the middle of the 8th century, fundamental changes took place in the system of international relations. The western part of the "Silk Road" came under Arab control. By the 13th century, Genghis Khan took control of all the branches of the Silk Road. This situation continued until the middle of the XIV century. During the rule of the Mongols, the merchants of Khorezm under Mahmud Yalovoch played the main role.[1]

If mainly silk and paper were exported from China to the Western countries through the "Silk Road", from the beginning of the Middle Ages, glass, all kinds of woolen fabrics, carpets, rugs, glass were exported to China from these countries. ,

metal, jewelry, precious stones, various medicines, purple horses are presented. Through these trade routes, Chinese bronze mirrors and square coins spread widely to the regions of the Ferghana Valley and the middle basin of the Syrdarya. The Great Silk Road was not only economically important, but it was also a road that spread the achievements of religious and cultural heritage and ensured diplomatic relations between countries. For example, Indian Buddhism entered China through Central Asia in this way. In the IV-VIII centuries, China's trade relations with the outside world expanded. During the period of early feudalism, sericulture developed in China, and silks entered Central Asia at a cheap price through Sughd merchants. They are not considered to be the rich stratum of the society who buy goods, sell goods and profit from them, but are merchants, diplomats, spreaders of knowledge who go on long journeys with large trade caravans, influential people who bring advanced economic inventions from one or another region to new places. was considered At the same time, they also acted as highly alert state spies, having a deep knowledge of the traditions, power and strength, territorial location, nature and state management system of other countries. Heads of state planned their foreign policies based on their observational skills and information. Such great and necessary works were carried out thanks to these trade and caravan routes. From the Melodic era to the 9th century, the Sogdian language rose to the level of a world trade language within the framework of the Silk Roads. As the "Silk Road" Central Asia played the role of intermediary between the East and the West, the migration

process intensified here, large groups of Turkic ethnic elements appeared and their penetration into the interior regions of Central Asia. accelerated. The contribution of Turkic-speaking peoples increased in the world of the Early Iranian language group, and by the 10th-11th centuries, the Turkic language environment became dominant in Movarounnahr, Khorezm and Eastern Khorasan (on the territory of Turkmenistan).

At the end of the XIV-XV centuries, Movarounnahr, the center of the Timurid state, was connected with large cities and countries of Europe, the Near and Far East through many caravan routes. These roads, which were founded long ago and in the period under consideration by energetic nomads, brave traders and intrepid tourists from different countries, were the main communication routes that carried out the political and economic relations of Timur and the Timurid state. Consequently, the caravan routes from different countries to Movarounnahr also served for military campaigns of the Timurids. In general, it is possible to identify some of the caravan routes from Movarounnahr to the neighboring regions, observing some of the routes of Timur's military campaigns for the campaigns carried out for different purposes. Timur, who aimed to create a great state, knew the importance of the caravan routes at that time and masterfully used them in his foreign policy. Khorezm, which was economically, politically and culturally in common with Movarounnahr in ancient times, was divided into two parts during the Mongol period, the northern Khorezm Golden Horde centered on the city of Urganch, and the southern Khorezm Chigatoy centered on the Kat fortress. looked at the ulus. At the end of the 60s of

the 14th century, the Kanghai Sufi dynasty ruled in northern Khorezm and united the northern and southern Khorezm lands. Meanwhile, Khorezm was economically and politically dependent on the Golden Horde.[2] Timur considered the whole of Khorezm to be an integral part of the Chigatai ulus and wanted to acquire the Silk Road passing through its territory. During the years 1372-1388, Timur marched 5 times to Khorezm, putting an end to feudal disunity and conflicts in Movarounnahr and Khorezm, and united the peoples living in the lands along the Syr Darya River to the Aral Sea under a single state. Amir Timur ruled the country for 35 years. He carried out many military campaigns and battles. Many countries were conquered. As a result, he created a vast kingdom that covered a huge area from India and China to the Black Sea and from the Aral Sea to the Persian Gulf. In addition, he conquered the countries of Asia Minor, Syria, Egypt and the Lower Volga, the banks of the Don, Lake Balkhash and the Ila River, as far as Northern India. During his many years of military campaigns, Timur attached special importance to the prosperity of Movarounnahr, the central part of his kingdom, especially the capital Samarkand, for the glory of his kingdom. For this purpose, he brought a lot of artisans, artists and scientists from the conquered countries along with material wealth to Movarounnahr as captives and forcibly used them for the development of the country. It was customary for Timur to celebrate every triumphant event and joyful event by building a magnificent architectural monument. Clavijo, the Spanish ambassador, wrote: he did not allow a single craftsman to leave

Movarounnahr. On the contrary, by the order of Temur, the most skilled weavers of Damascus, the famous cotton picker of Aleppo, the best weaving enterprises of Ankara, goldsmiths of Turkey and Georgia, in short, many craftsmen were moved from other cities to Samarkand. He not only improved Movarounnahr and Turkestan, but also rebuilt the cities of conquered countries. Robots, castles, bridges were built on caravan routes, mosques and madrassas and gardens were built in cities. The caravan roads were cleared of bandits. In order to ensure the safety of passengers, he built settlements for their passage. In order to create convenience, he placed guards on the main roads. Guards were responsible for passengers' belongings. Most importantly, he ended the feudal disunity and conflict in Iran, Azerbaijan and Iraq, and restored the ancient caravan routes connecting the East and the West.[3]

As a result of the disintegration of the USSR leading to a crisis, the former republics of the former USSR will become independent states. Currently, the countries that have gained independence are actively participating in the world economy at the international level and have economic, political, and cultural relations with all the countries of the world. The countries of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan located in Central Asia are now gradually entering the world economy.[4] The role of the "Great Silk Road" is extremely important for Central Asian countries in entering the world economy. We know very well how important road, railway, sea and air routes are in the economy of every country. Depending on the geographical location of the country, the importance of different roads varies. In

the republics of Central Asia, which are located in a closed basin far from the seas, road and railway transport are mainly used for cargo transportation. In the current period of technical progress and rapid economic development, we are not satisfied with economic relations only with neighboring countries. We need to export our goods to world markets, we need to import goods to our domestic markets. For this, in addition to road and rail transport, we must also use sea transport. The closest sea route to Central Asian countries is the Black Sea. In May 1993, a meeting of representatives of the European Commission, Central Asian and Caucasian countries, as well as the European Union countries was held in Brussels. The issue of building the Europe-Caucasus-Asia transport corridor "TRASEKA" connecting Europe and Asia was discussed there. It can be said that this meeting was the first practical step in restoring the "Great Silk Road". Until now, 50 countries of the world deliver their goods to their destinations through TRACEKA roads. Both the East and the West will benefit from these roads. A wide path to the world market will open for Central Asia and the Caucasus. Uzbekistan is located at the main link of this road connecting Europe and Asia. The location of our country in the center of the countries of Central Asia and Kazakhstan has been the reason for the passage of the busiest routes of the "Silk Road" since ancient times. Even now, most of the roads and railways connecting Central Asia with Europe and Asia pass through the territory of our country. Currently, the Tashkent-Andijan-Osh-Irkeshtom-Kashkar road is being built at a rapid pace. The main part of this road corresponds to the territory of Uzbekistan. This road connects the largest

cities of Europe and Asia, that is, Paris and Shanghai. Since ancient times, the roads between the countries have been built in all the most convenient places. The "Great Silk Road" also passed through sandy deserts, high mountains, and endless steppes, connecting cities and villages. Most of the current highways correspond to the "Silk Road". In September 1998, an international conference on the development of the Europe-Caucasus-Asia transport corridor (TRACEKA) was held in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan. Leaders of 32 countries and representatives of more than 10 international organizations took part in it. The first President of our republic, I.A. Karimov, explained the importance of the TRASEKA project as follows: the implementation of the TRASEKA project made it possible for us to go to both the Western and Eastern sea routes, and our export and import goods will be much cheaper. The entry of European and Asian countries into the markets of the Caucasus and Central Asia will be opened. The entry into force of the TRASEKA project will enable the implementation of other similar projects. This creates conditions for further strengthening of trade relations with countries in Europe and Asia-Pacific region. We would not be mistaken if we call most of the roads built according to the projects the restoration of the "Great Silk Road".[5]

With the complete restoration of the "Great Silk Road" in a new content and qualities, completely new sources of development, factors and opportunities will appear for the peoples of European and Asian countries. They can expand even further and help to solve the most serious environmental problem - the problem of the Aral Sea.

Summary: In conclusion, it can be said that with the full restoration of the "Great Silk Road", first of all, trade relations between countries will strengthen, the volume of trade will increase, and they will have a positive effect on economic development. New enterprises, modern technical stations and service branches will be created, and the productive forces of the countries will develop. As a result of scientific and technical relations and the introduction of new techniques and technologies, scientific and technical progress will be accelerated, the competitiveness of farms and goods will increase. Many new jobs will be created and they will multiply, many of the unemployed will have their own jobs. Within each country and internationally, the division of labor deepens and expands, new types of work and new professions emerge. National and international relations will change and improve. Opportunities to improve the ecological environment and increase the quality of goods will expand. The conditions and factors that influence the economic growth of the production, sale and purchase of products, export and import, will expand even more. As a result of this, people's material life improves and their material well-being increases. Cultural, spiritual and educational relations and contacts between peoples, including educational tourism, will further develop and improve. All-round development of all nations will increase. The growth of economic, spiritual-educational and other relations has a positive effect on political relations between countries and peoples, on the international situation, and international peace and cooperation will increase.

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